

The Marie Curie Alumni Association announces its support for Plan S

The much anticipated “Plan S” which outlines a future strategy for Open Science (OS) in Europe was recently announced.¹

“On 4 September 2018, 11 national research funding organisation, with the support of the European Commission, including the European Research Council (ERC), announced the launch of cOAlition S, an initiative to make full and immediate Open Access to research publications a reality. It is built around Plan S, which consists of one target and 10 principles.”

The Marie Curie Alumni Association (MCAA) is a strong supporter of OS and actively promotes OS among its members, researchers and the wider society. As a recently published MCAA recommendation on the future of European Research funding stresses, the MCAA considers OS as one of the most important pillars of the future framework programme Horizon Europe.²

The MCAA hereby announces its support for Plan S, commends all funders and stakeholders that are contributing to its development and implementation, and encourages all funding organizations to participate in, and facilitate the widespread and full implementation of, open access publication. We also encourage all EU countries and research funding bodies to adopt the principles of Plan S and congratulates the entities who are already part of cOAlition S.³

The implementation of Plan S will require major adaptation and changes in the research community in almost all aspects of scholarly work, including scientific publication, scholarly communication, research data management, and research evaluation and funding—as discussed in our recent policy paper.²

Plan S acknowledges the importance to further develop required support for researchers and research institutions to adopt open access policies. This includes suitable open access infrastructure, especially for less well-funded researchers and research institutions and funding to offset any publication-related costs. Challenges and open questions remain for how to best achieve this.

The MCAA is strongly committed to encourage and facilitate these advances. Therefore, the MCAA remains an active contributor to this important discussion and is open to provide input and aid in the development of good practices.

¹ <http://scieur.org/plan-s>

² <https://www.mariecuriealumni.eu/future-framework-programme-horizon-europe-your-hands>

³ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/commissioners/2014-2019/moedas/announcements/plan-s-and-coalition-s-accelerating-transition-full-and-immediate-open-access-scientific_en

Information about this press release

This document was prepared by the MCAA Policy Working Group and approved for release by the Chair of the MCAA Board on September 5, 2018. This document is released under a CC BY 4.0 license.⁴

Information about the Marie Curie Alumni Association

The Marie Skłodowska-Curie actions (MSCA) is one of the European Union's flagship initiatives to provide research grants supporting researchers at all stages of their careers, across all disciplines.⁵ MSCA fellowships are among Europe's most competitive and prestigious awards, aimed to support the best, most promising researchers.

The Marie Curie Alumni Association (MCAA) is a global network of researchers open to any past or present researchers supported by the MSCA.⁶ The MCAA has over 10 000 registered members, and represents the over 100 000 researchers that have been supported by the MSCA over the last two decades.⁷ The MCAA is a non-profit, politically and commercially independent organization, supported through funding from the European Union.

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⁴ <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/research/mariecurieactions/>

⁶ <https://www.mariecuriealumni.eu/>

⁷ http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_IP-17-426_en.htm